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Integrating Human Capital and Institutional Governance of the Creative Industry to Mitigate Unemployment, Poverty, and Inequality

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ABSTRACT

Integrating human capital capacity and institutional governance in the creative industry is mitigating sustainable development issues. Therefore, this study aimed to explain the integration of human capital capacity development and the integrity of institutional governance quality to mitigate unemployment, poverty, and inequality. A two-step mixed-methods design was adopted, comprising both exploratory and explanatory designs. Experimental and phenomenological methods complemented the analytical study method. The results showed that institutional integrity and human capital capacity were the key to mitigating unemployment, poverty, and inequality. Partially, inequality could be mitigated through the expansion of employment opportunities in the creative industry across various underdeveloped regions, drawing on available human capital capacity. The integration and collaboration model between human capital capacity and quality institutional governance, with integrity and without corruption, was also more effective in mitigating unemployment, poverty, and inequality, catalyzing sustainable development. The implications of these results could inform the development of institutional regulations and policies in addressing the main problems of sustainable development.

Keywords: unemployment, poverty, inequality, human capital, and institutions.

INTRODUCTION

The complex interconnectedness of unemployment, poverty, and inequality is a fundamental sustainable development issue that remains difficult to resolve (Twalo, 2024; Thorbecke et al., 2024; Deshmukh et al., 2025; Soliman and Beram, 2026; Zehri and Ammar, 2026). Meanwhile, extreme poverty is a multidimensional challenge that cannot be resolved solely through a sectoral method (Widyawati et al., 2025). Poverty is even more difficult to resolve when unemployment and inequality persist (Prasetyo et al., 2026a). According to a previous study, reducing unemployment can simultaneously mitigate poverty (Prasetyo and Cahyani, 2022). Despite the rate of unemployment reduction, global and national poverty in Indonesia continues to slow. However, the fundamental problem of inequality between individuals, regions, and nations, nationally and globally, remains high, making the issue difficult to address. A previous study suggested that complementing the quality of human capital with the integrity of institutional governance was increasingly effective at mitigating the fundamental issue in sustainable development (Prasetyo et al., 2026b). This was because human capital information systems were an effective tool used for integration by most modern organizations (Rubavathi and Balamurugan, 2024).

Various institutional economic policies are increasingly important in mitigating the three fundamental development challenges. However, low-quality, non-integrated institutions, due to widespread corruption, worsen the development challenges (Abbas et al., 2023; Rudiyanisah & Rezki, 2025; Pham, 2025; Hamdene and Neffati, 2025; Hartwig and Sturm, 2025; Mubangizi, 2025; Fabrizio, 2026). According to previous studies, human capital and institutional quality can increasingly enhance technological and social innovation as catalysts for sustainable development (Prasetyo et al., 2026b; Odei and Soukal, 2026). Abbas et al. (2023) found that institutional quality has a significant and beneficial effect on reducing income inequality. However, corruption further degrades institutional quality and substantially increases income inequality. Institutional corruption in the workplace is an important social phenomenon, characterized by numerous conflicts of interest, including both individual and organizational actors, and deserving of further investigation (Schulz AW, 2026). The correlation among human capital capacity, institutional quality, and unemployment rates varies across sectors, necessitating a more targeted policy focus (Vicente, 2023). This is because institutional quality and institutional trust interact dynamically over time (Dileo et al., 2026). Empirically, low institutional quality is detrimental to poverty eradication, suggesting that human capital capacity is only moderately effective in reducing poverty (Goh et al., 2024). A previous study also reported that educational achievement produced only limited success (Gaur et al., 2026).

Based on the background, this study aimed to explain the importance of integrating human capital capacity and institutional governance quality in the creative industry to mitigate unemployment, poverty, and inequality. Evidence from previous empirical studies showed a causal relationship, particularly among unemployment, poverty, and inequality (Ajide et al., 2025; Parsons and Rabhi, 2025). Recent studies recommended that multidimensional analysis of inequality to uncover differences was increasingly important compared to analyses based solely on income (Kapera et al., 2026; Purwaningsih et al., 2025). Institutional quality, inclusive economic growth, and human capital capacity are mutually reinforcing solutions (Raifu., et al., 2026). This study contributes to explaining the integration of human capital capacity with quality institutional governance with integrity as a mitigation tool for fundamental development problems and a catalyst for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economist Dudley Seers (1920-1983) stated that the goal of development is to reduce unemployment, poverty, and inequality. The persistence or worsening of even one of these three core problems shows that development cannot be considered successful. Seers advocated a human capital-centred method to development, supported by multidisciplinary perspectives and socio-economically relevant institutional policies. Such policies require institutions with the capacity to formulate and implement effective solutions to these challenges. In this case, human capital is defined as a socio-economic asset due to the ability to provide significant added economic value and social equity (Prasetyo et al., 2026b). The theories of new institutional economics (NIE) and human capital capacity form the basis of this study's discussion (Prasetyo and Kistanti, 2020; Zhu and Li, 2024). Integrating these theories fosters entrepreneurial performance in the creative industries and drives innovation, creating various job opportunities and social networks, thereby reducing unemployment and poverty (Prasetyo & Kistanti, 2020; Prasetyo et al., 2026a). Consequently, high-quality, sustainable economic development can increasingly be achieved through four pillars, namely human and social capital, as well as institutions and entrepreneurial innovation (Prasetyo and Kistanti, 2020).

Modern theory posits that institutions and human capital, supported by technology and innovation, are fundamental drivers of high-quality long-term economic growth (Acemoglu et al., 2026a). Low adoption and diffusion of technological innovation due to weaknesses in the education system, poor governance practices, and institutional distortions such as corruption hinder the achievement of high-quality development in both the short and long term (Prasetyo et al., 2026b; Acemoglu et al., 2026a; 2026b). However, there is no single theoretical foundation that is complete and perfect to address all the fundamental problems of quality development without unemployment, poverty, and inequality. The novelty of this study is in the method, which integrates theoretical foundations holistically and multidimensionally. The basic premise is that human capital capacity theory plays an increasingly important role in shaping technological innovation and institutions, regardless of whether those institutions are right or wrong (Zhu and Li, 2024; Prasetyo & Kistanti, 2020). In this study, the method's novelty is in the use of governance integrity, institutional quality, and human capital capacity as the fundamental dimensions of a new theory (Acemoglu et al., 2026b; Prasetyo et al., 2026b). Theoretically, economic development based on human capital capacity will increasingly effectively strengthen the integrity of new, stronger institutions (Abrha and Brhane, 2025; Cinnirella & Streb, 2017).

A renowned economist, Amartya Sen (1969), recommended enhancing human capability development and showed the crucial role of institutions, such as the state, society, and family. Institutions are not final goals but serve as crucial instruments for achieving human development. Previous studies have confirmed significant relationships among human capital capacity, institutional quality, global integration, and increased economic competitiveness (Prasetyo et al., 2025). Important policies are needed to measure the complementary roles of human capital and institutional quality (Prasetyo et al., 2025). Other results have complemented the theoretical foundations of human capital and institutional quality for this study. These results suggest the need for a comprehensive governance theory capable of reducing poverty and increasing human capital capacity (Ahmad et al., 2018; Moyo et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2026). Other studies show that increasing human capital capacity and the quality of institutional governance integrity can drive inclusive and high-quality economic growth (Prasetyo, 2020; Ofori et al., 2024). However, negative governance dynamics completely negate the positive impact of human capital in driving inclusive economic growth (Ofori et al., 2024). Integrity in institutional governance will further strengthen the benefits of human capital capacity for financial inclusion and develop a more conducive environment for banking institutions and digital financial platforms (Khan et al., 2025). This is because financial development has led to greater inequality and more poverty (Sturm, et al., 2025).

METHODS

Accurate and relevant methods were required to achieve the study objectives. A two-step mixed-methods design was used, comprising exploratory and explanatory. The advantages and implications of a two-step mixed-methods design extended beyond simply connecting data or synthesizing results from different analytical procedures, focusing instead on a more feasible integration with experimental methods (Creamer et al., 2025). Experimental methods were more helpful for understanding and addressing these difficulties because beliefs were more endogenous (Camera et al., 2025; Harton, 2025; Boehm et al., 2025). The phenomenological method was used to synchronize study cost efficiency further, but there was still potential for integration with mixed-methods design (Adeniran and Tayo, 2024; Martiny et al., 2021). The quadruple-helix integration and collaboration method in this study was considered novel, and only the triple-helix was partially used. This study used the linkage method, the convergence model, and an integration of industrial resource theory (Prasetyo et al., 2021; Harahap, 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Previous studies have shown that the three fundamental development issues, namely unemployment, poverty, and inequality, are generally highly complex and difficult to resolve (Prasetyo et al., 2026a). However, this empirical study further reinforces that the underlying issue of inequality remains the most complex and difficult to resolve. Theoretically and empirically, unemployment remains the easiest to resolve, and reducing it can further contribute to poverty alleviation (Prasetyo and Thomas, 2021). Improving the quality of human capital and strengthening institutional governance remained key challenges. Inadequate and poorly directed results for human capital capacity-building further worsened conditions across society, including the creative industry. These issues were compounded by corrupt actors within institutional governance who lack integrity. As previously explained, the result showed that even with a high Government Spending value (91.4%), the country had a high level of freedom. However, because the values of government institutional integrity, labor freedom, and investment freedom were suppressed, the huge Government Spending was unable to address core development issues adequately. The values of Government Integrity, Labor Freedom, and Investment Freedom were still below 50% (repressed), namely 3.95, 49.3, and 45.0, respectively (Prasetyo & Kistanti, 2020). This showed that corruption cases in Indonesia have worsened, particularly in government integrity, investment freedom, and worker freedom, all of which were increasingly suppressed. Poor and unintegrated institutional governance integrity further complicated existing conditions and increased structural poverty. Economic growth driven by poor institutions lacking integrity due to widespread corruption led to further structural impoverishment of society and worsened existing inequality. The greater the level of corruption occurring through market and institutional mechanisms, the more complex the underlying problems of sustainable development become. Corrupt actors were currently obscuring corruption through market mechanisms.

Substantial government spending could be better used to address the underlying development issues of reducing unemployment, poverty, and inequality if there were integrity and good institutional governance. However, due to low government integrity, the spending remained inefficient and failed to address underlying development issues. For example, while Indonesia's economic growth in the first quarter of 2026 reached 5.61%, driven largely by government spending, it proved unable to address the three underlying development issues. In Indonesia, policy implementation has tended to favor banks, with funds being directed primarily to this sector and, to a lesser extent, to the creative industry. This decision of institutional policies showed injustice. In the long term, the unfair policies increasingly impacted the industrial sector, depriving it of independence, sovereignty, and competitiveness. Most industrial sectors in Indonesia were highly dependent on imported raw materials. Because industrial products were not export-oriented, frequent depreciation of the rupiah against the US dollar did not benefit the industrial sector and instead worsened its condition. These unfair policies worsened the industrial situation and accelerated premature deindustrialization in Indonesia. Therefore, this study aimed to explain the policy regulations for increasing human capital capacity that should be synergistic and integrated with the integrity of the quality of collaborative and convergent creative industry institutional governance to mitigate the main development problems. Based on the study results in Table 1, human-capital capacity (HCi) made the largest contribution, accounting for 44.23% of quality and inclusive economic growth (EGi). This was compared with institutional governance integrity (IGi) at 37.45% and social-economic capital (SCi) at 19.14%.

Table 1: The regression model analysis results for the path of quality and inclusive economic growth

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R-Square		Std. Error of the Estimate		Durbin-Watson	
1	0.9680 ^b	0.9359	0.9267		9.77519		1.9482	
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t-stc	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	5.024	1.4732			3.4114	0.001		
H <i>C</i> _i	33.1352	3.8391	0.4423		8.6312	0.000	0.3742	2.6722
1 I <i>G</i> _i	31.4452	4.7905	0.3745		6.5653	0.000	0.3035	3.3021
SC <i>i</i>	17.0061	4.5124	0.1914		3.7693	0.000	0.3834	2.6143

a. Dependent Variable: E*G*_i

b. Predictors: (Constant), H*C*_i, I*G*_i, SC*i*)

The results supported the standard theory that mitigating unemployment, poverty, and inequality could be achieved through high-quality, inclusive economic growth based on human capital capacity and institutional integrity. Therefore, implementing macroeconomic policies to address unemployment, poverty, and inequality cannot be done solely on the aggregate demand side, namely through monetary and fiscal policies. Macroeconomic policies should also be implemented on the aggregate supply side, with policies to increase production capacity by strengthening human capital production factors and the integrity of related institutional governance across sectors of life. This study integrated human capital factors and institutional governance integrity in the creative industry to reduce the core problems of unemployment, poverty, and inequality. The results suggested that the easiest way to achieve the objective was to first reduce unemployment, both directly and indirectly, through inclusive, high-quality economic growth and increased investment in human capital capacity, thereby simultaneously reducing poverty. Although extreme poverty was a multidisciplinary challenge, it was more effectively addressed through an integrated sectoral method that built human capital capacity and strengthened the integrity of relevant institutional governance. Reducing the underlying problem of inequality remained quite difficult to achieve partially.

The results show that the integrity of institutional governance and human capital capacity were key factors in reducing unemployment, poverty, and inequality. Meanwhile, the best way to mitigate inequality was to develop many job opportunities in creative industries across various underdeveloped regions, based on human capital capacity and the integrity of institutional governance. This could be done by developing appropriate innovations and technologies inclusively, supported by high-quality human capital. Furthermore, active participation through a model of integration and collaboration among related institutions sourced from human capital capacity will further promote high-quality, inclusive economic growth. Figure 1 shows the proposed integration and collaboration model to overcome this problem. The Quadruple method in this study was a new basic concept of strategic integration and collaboration that included four related basic institutional environment elements, namely Academic, Business/Industry, Government, and Community Social Institutional Environment.

Figur-1: Institutional quintuple helix convergence, integration and collaboration model solutions

The result of this study is expected to contribute to strategic policymaking for synergistic human capital capacity development through the integrity and quality of institutional governance in the creative industry. The solution was implemented through an integrated model that collaborated and integrated relevant institutions. The main objective was to mitigate key development challenges while promoting quality and inclusive economic growth. However, further strengthening synergistic human capital capacity required attention to more specific and relevant strategic policy subsystem models within a sustainable process. Strategic policy regulation for human capital capacity development cannot rely solely on formal education but must also be consistent with different levels of expertise and skills. Quality education that built human capital capacity was not derived solely from formal education but was also shaped by diverse experiences and character-based education, which acted as key drivers of social innovation, development, and social change. These results supported previous studies suggesting a dynamic and reciprocal relationship between education and social development (Bhuyan, 2026). Meanwhile, innovative comprehensive study methods designed to build human capital capacity and institutional governance could be implemented through the model described in Figure 1.

The results further supported the recommendation of the previous study that policy implementation focused more on enhancing human capital development with high integrity to promote good, high-integrity industrial institutional governance. However, this study did not specify a concrete model for enhancing human capital capacity development. Based on phenomenological results, priority was given to character development and intangible assets, such as honesty and integrity, as components of human capital. More focus was placed on strengthening the core function of human capital in relation to the quality of institutional governance. Increased human capital capacity was considered more capable of mitigating unemployment and poverty. Theoretically and empirically, human capital capacity-building was expected to generate new job opportunities and reduce poverty. Empirical evidence showed that human capital capacity did not automatically reduce inequality, as increased

educational attainment did not strictly translate into higher productivity and competitiveness. Weak human capital capacity and poor institutional governance were found to hinder quality and inclusive economic growth. Consequently, addressing fundamental development challenges was unlikely to succeed in contexts where institutions lacked integrity due to widespread corruption.

More interesting results from a phenomenological analysis of efforts to reduce unemployment, poverty, and inequality showed that integrating human capital capacity and institutional governance integrity through collaborative work functioned as an interdependent pathway. The empirical study results, through the lived experiences of the sample respondents, phenomenologically identify that capacity, mindset, attitudes, behavioral skills, life experience, perseverance, and the integrity of a strong institutional framework for governance were important catalysts for inclusive economic growth through socio-economic mobility within the community. Based on a phenomenological perspective, unemployment and poverty were not only a matter of insufficient income. An institutional governance framework that prioritized integrity and a corruption-free method was more effective at reducing inequality. This study confirmed that increasing human capital capacity was more effective at addressing unemployment and poverty. Meanwhile, institutional governance that was integrity-driven and corruption-free was more effective at mitigating existing inequality. An integrated, collaborative method combining human capital capacity building with institutional governance that upheld integrity was more effective as a strategic solution to mitigate unemployment, poverty, and inequality, while also acting as a catalyst for sustainable development.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study explains that increasing human capital capacity is more effective at creating new job opportunities to reduce unemployment and promote quality, inclusive economic growth. Furthermore, increasing new job opportunities mitigates poverty issues. The integrity of quality institutional governance is better able to mitigate inequality issues. The results also show that integrating human capital capacity with institutional governance integrity in the creative industry simultaneously mitigates unemployment, poverty, and inequality, while also acting as a catalyst for quality, sustainable, inclusive economic growth. Greater synergy between institutional governance integrity and human capital capacity increases the ability to mitigate core sustainable development challenges. Corruption and a lack of institutional governance worsen the core issues of sustainable development and magnify the increasingly complex inequality. The implications of this study result can serve as a regulatory framework for related macroeconomic institutional policies to address the core issues of sustainable development. This shows that the implementation of macro policies to reduce inequality cannot be done solely on the aggregate demand side. However, policy implementation from the aggregate supply side is more appropriate for generating new job opportunities across related sectors in underdeveloped areas, based on human capital capacity.

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